

When Meshes lie

Formalising Tacit Knowledge for Flaw Recognition in Cultural Heritage Photogrammetry

[Blind Author]

Abstract

This article presents a methodological framework for the semantic characterisation of surface flaws in photogrammetric 3D models, developed within Cultural Heritage digitisation workflows. Rather than relying on pre-defined classifications or automatic detection, the method captures expert corrections during mesh cleaning and formalises them as traceable, interpretable annotations. Through a retroprojection mechanism, these interventions are mapped back onto the pre-corrected model, producing a semantic segmentation of flaws grounded in situated expertise. Each flawed region is analysed using mesh-derived indicators—such as PCA-based descriptors, edge length, and photogrammetric confidence—to identify recurring patterns of deviation. This process supports the construction of a frequency-based taxonomy of common artefacts, structured across low-, mid-, and high-frequency classes and illustrated with real-world examples. The taxonomy does not aim to provide exhaustive coverage or prescriptive correction strategies but serves as a proof of concept for encoding tacit judgement into a reproducible descriptive system. The approach is applied to a single-operator dataset and is presented as a foundational step toward reproducible flaw annotation and structured paradata integration. While further validation across operators and use cases is required, the method already offers a means to bridge procedural opacity and semantic clarity, particularly in workflows where dissemination assets derive from documentation-oriented models. By aligning mesh geometry, operator intervention, and scalar descriptors, the framework establishes a basis for more transparent assessment, future comparative validation, and potential integration into semi-automated classification systems. It also contributes to the ongoing effort to embed semantic meaning and interpretive traceability directly within 3D assets..

Keywords

Photogrammetry; 3D Mesh Processing; Flaw Recognition; Tacit Knowledge; Cultural Heritage Digitisation; Semantic Annotation; PCA Analysis; Paradata Integration.

Highlights

- Raw digitised 3D meshes often contain features that are in fact artefacts
 - Morphometric analysis helps identify mesh artefacts created during processing
 - Expert knowledge is tacit and unstructured, but can be explicit and organised
 - Correction steps act as a tool to detect and classify mesh imperfections
 - Each step of the pipeline builds a traceable and interpretable data structure
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1. Introduction

1.1 Digitisation of CH

The digitisation of tangible Cultural Heritage serves two concurrent purposes: documentation and dissemination. While the former aims to construct a dense and traceable representation of the object's physical configuration, the latter prioritises accessibility, visual legibility, and platform compatibility.

These two purposes are not mutually exclusive. Nonetheless, in many institutional workflows, models generated for documentation are later adapted for dissemination through processes rarely subject to the same level of scrutiny. Derived assets are often treated as secondary outputs, requiring no further validation. Paradoxically, this undermines their communicative power, precisely where effectiveness and clarity are most critical.

As a result, rigour tends to be neglected even when documentation was the primary intent, due to the lack of structured methods for controlling and communicating surface quality throughout the transformation chain. The present work stems from this observation and proposes a descriptive framework to make such flaws recognisable, classifiable, and ultimately accountable. In particular, it redefines the correction phase (Figure 1) not as a mere cleaning step, but as the epistemic moment in which flaws are detected, delimited, and semantically qualified.

The London Charter (2009) explicitly frames digital representations as scholarly outputs, requiring methodological clarity and full documentation of the processes involved. Complementing this perspective, the Seville Principles (2017) stress the epistemological responsibility of virtual archaeology, highlighting the need for plausible and well-argued interpretation of the available evidence as paradata (Bentkowska-Kafel & Denard, 2016). Yet, as noted by Koller et al. (2010), current infrastructures and tools often fail to operationalise these principles, especially in the early stages of 3D data processing and mesh inspection.

These limitations are particularly evident in low-cost or semi-automated workflows, where the lack of control over intermediate steps can obscure the provenance and quality of the resulting models (Remondino et al., 2012). This control can be partially restored by explicitly documenting the interpretive operations performed during defect remediation, transforming them into traceable and analysable actions within a structured framework.

As a form of measurement, every digital model, hereafter asset, represents an approximation of the physical object, hereafter item, and is inevitably a simplification, since perfect equivalence is unattainable. Environmental and operational factors further affect the process beyond instrumental limitations, introducing discrete, localised, and often non-systematic errors. These become embedded in the asset, making every digital transposition inherently flawed.

Research has developed techniques to identify and correct such errors, often by analysing local anomaly neighbourhoods. While effective for simple geometries, these approaches often fall short with the complex forms typical of Cultural Heritage. In such cases, expert intervention becomes essential: cleaning is performed manually or semi-automatically (Botsch et al., 2010), based on interpretive judgement and comparison with the item. Final accuracy thus depends not only on tools, but on domain-specific expertise.

This leads to a paradox: from a metrological standpoint, the raw asset is the most rigorous, as it derives directly from traceable procedures; yet it is also the least reliable, due to discrete, non-systematic errors. Raw assets are often visually unattractive and computationally heavy. A standard practice has therefore emerged: retaining the raw asset as a specialist master and producing optimised versions for dissemination (Gaiani, 2011).

However, in the absence of shared terminology and formalised classification of mesh defects, expert corrective actions remain undocumented, their rationale implicit. This work addresses that gap by reframing the correction phase not as a neutral refinement step, but as a critical interpretive stage. Here, flaws are not only removed but actively recognised, semantically delimited, and annotated through embedded segmentation.

Mesh-derived indicators, such as Curvature proxies, Edge Length, and photogrammetric confidence, serve as heuristic supports, enabling experts to ground their interventions in verifiable geometric evidence. This process yields a traceable map of the reasoning applied, allowing the extraction of recurring flaw patterns and supporting the construction of a preliminary taxonomy. While not prescriptive, this taxonomy demonstrates how semantic segmentation can emerge from situated expertise and be anchored to measurable surface behaviour—laying the groundwork for reproducible annotation, interpretive transparency, and future validation strategies.

Fig. 1: The asset “Lophius Piscatorius” before (left) and, after (right) manual corrections. The corrected model is here shown untextured to show the complexity of the model’s geometric features. Screenshot from Zbrush.

1.2 From Raw to Readable: Balancing Documentation and Dissemination

The distinction between documentation and dissemination is historically grounded in technological constraints: to publish 3D content online or in interactive environments, models had to be aggressively simplified to ensure compatibility and responsiveness. While this rationale still underpins many workflows, advances in rendering pipelines, data transmission protocols, and Web3D platforms have significantly relaxed such limitations.

Today, dissemination-oriented assets are still routinely derived from documented models, often through opaque simplification or ad hoc optimisation strategies that disregard semantic and morphological integrity. Consequently, it becomes unclear which features of the original model have been preserved, discarded, or distorted, and why. This opacity stems not only from geometric simplification, but also from the absence of traceable segmentation: interpretive decisions, such as which flaws to remove, and how, are rarely recorded, leaving downstream users with visually convincing but epistemologically ungrounded assets.

This critique does not imply that dissemination-oriented campaigns are inherently flawed, nor that all digital models must adhere to documentary standards. Digitisation processes vary widely in purpose, scale, and methodological ambition: models intended for storytelling, education, or immersive interaction may legitimately prioritise perceptual or experiential qualities. In such cases, simplification is not only acceptable, but often required. However, even when dissemination is the primary goal, acquisition remains, de facto, a form of documentation. Making interpretive operations explicit therefore strengthens not only scholarly transparency, but also communicative reliability. This is especially true when dissemination assets are derived from documentation-oriented workflows, or when multiple uses are foreseen. In such hybrid or repurposed contexts, methodological traceability becomes crucial, not to impose a universal standard, but to support informed reuse and critical evaluation

Technologies such as public 3D repositories based on WebGL/Web3D, metadata-rich formats like glTF (Blinded for Review 5), browser-accessible content, and remote streaming solutions are opening new scenarios not only for museum communication but also for collaborative research. Within this framework, maintaining a strict separation between scientific and disseminative assets becomes a limitation—hampering both the quality of communication and the opportunity to accelerate and democratise research.

To address this, the proposed framework embeds semantic segmentation—understood here as the manual tagging of surface regions based on their meaning or function, directly within the correction phase, marking flawed areas through polygroups before any optimisation occurs. This allows the derived asset to retain not only its visual plausibility, but also a documented record of the interpretive process that shaped it, enabling verification, review, and reuse..

1.3 Towards a Unified Asset for Documentation and Dissemination.

To overcome the aforementioned dichotomy, raw assets should be cleaned and optimised through a controlled process that preserves both geometric consistency and interpretive transparency. In such a framework, the master asset should no longer coincide with the raw acquisition model but rather take the form of a cleaned and optimised version that combines technical robustness with visual usability, while also preserving an embedded record of the interpretive decisions made during the correction process. In Blinded for review (1), this principle was already addressed through a structured revision pipeline based on four stages (Figure 2):

- *RAW*: refers to all unprocessed data directly obtained from the instruments.
- *RAWp*: (*RAW* processed) refers to the data transformed into a textured mesh and then globally filtered through automated procedures to remove well-known and clearly characterised defects.
- *DCHO*: (*D*igital *C*ultural *H*eritage *O*bject) is the cleaned model, free from flaws and gaps. It may not preserve the full data density of the *RAWp* model, as cleaning and simplification can occur simultaneously.
- *DCHOo*: (*DCHO* optimised) is the final optimised and metadata-enriched model, prepared for publication in glTF format.

This multi-stage pipeline progressively introduces semantic control: from automatic filtering in *RAWp* to expert-guided correction and annotation in *DCHO*, where flaws are manually addressed and—ideally—segmented in a traceable way.

In the present proposal, this structure is retained with one critical variation: *DCHO* is required to preserve the full data content of *RAWp*, with simplification strictly deferred to the *DCHOo* phase. This enforces a rigorous separation between cleaning and optimisation, making *DCHO* the definitive master asset, balanced for both Documentation and Dissemination. Within this structure, however, a key bottleneck persists in the transition from *RAWp* to *DCHO*—namely, the need to systematically identify, classify, and eliminate acquisition-induced defects, which are often addressed heuristically and without formal traceability.

Previous developments have partially addressed this gap. In Blinded for Review (2), the correction of mesh voids was explicitly annotated to preserve interpretive traceability, while Blinded for Review (3) introduced a projection-based method to detect such gaps by comparing *RAWp* and *DCHO* geometries. A preliminary outline of the present methodology, focused on leveraging expert corrections as a source of semantic information within the *RAWp*–*DCHO* transition, was presented by the author in a two-page extended abstract submitted to the conference (blinded for review). While that version anticipated the core rationale and its integration within the established *RAW* → *DCHOo* pipeline, it remained conceptual and limited in scope.

Building on these foundations, the present article generalises the approach to encompass all corrective operations. It introduces a unified system that captures tacit operator knowledge during the editing phase, annotates each intervention at the *DCHO* level, and projects these annotations back onto the *RAWp* mesh, where the original flaws are segmented, localised, and analysed using mesh-based indicators..

The resulting framework enables a reproducible classification of flawed regions—not by pre-correction inspection, but through interpretive feedback grounded in actual expert practice. These correspondences support a double semantic stratification: *RAWp* is structured by defect type, and *DCHO* by correction type, allowing both assets to be semantically and metrically aligned. This alignment forms the basis for the proposed taxonomy, which organises flaw categories according to morphological traits and mesh-derived metrics, providing a formal language for describing imperfections across diverse CH digitisation scenarios..

Fig. 2: The adopted workflow for mesh generation and optimisation in CH digitisation pipelines, as proposed in *Blinded for Review (1)*

1.4 Structure of the Paper

This paper is structured to clarify the conceptual scope of the proposed framework and to distinguish its contributions from existing approaches.

- *Section 2:* Situates the proposal within current literature, focusing on how flaw correction and operator-driven interventions are addressed in photogrammetric workflows.
- *Section 3:* Defines the epistemological premises and introduces the method, highlighting the role of tacit knowledge and mesh-based indicators in supporting interpretive decisions.
- *Section 4:* Details the mesh-based morphometric indicators used to support defect classification and enable reproducible, feedback-driven annotation.
- *Section 5:* Presents the taxonomy of flaw types derived from expert feedback, as a demonstrator of the framework and a proof of concept for a formalised descriptive language.
- *Section 6:* Concludes by discussing the method's implications, current limitations, and potential applications.

2. Related Works

2.1 Photogrammetry-Based Surface Reconstruction

Photogrammetry is widely used for the three-dimensional digitisation of Cultural Heritage (CH) assets, offering a flexible and cost-effective alternative to active scanning technologies (Apollonio et al., 2021). When acquisition is performed under controlled conditions, the method yields metrically accurate and visually rich 3D models. However, such conditions are rarely achievable in CH practice, particularly during large-scale

digitisation campaigns of temporary museum collections, as noted by Blinded for Review (4) and reflected in the forthcoming Guidelines for the 3D digitisation of Historical, Artistic and Museum Heritage (Linee guida, 2025).

Even when acquisition constraints are acknowledged, factors such as access limitations, suboptimal lighting, surface reflectivity, or time restrictions often result in irregular image sampling, occlusions, and misalignments. These issues originate in the photogrammetric point cloud and are typically propagated, sometimes amplified, into the mesh, introducing discrete, non-systematic errors that manifest as local morphological anomalies (Berger et al., 2016). Such artefacts may be perceptible to expert operators, but remain difficult to detect algorithmically due to their variability and lack of formal characterisation.

Importantly, not all local anomalies are flaws: some correspond to legitimate object features, especially at medium or high spatial frequencies. By contrast, flaws are artefacts that both violate expected morphological continuity and cannot be attributed to actual geometry. This ambiguity makes the distinction between flaw and feature non-trivial, reinforcing the need for a semantic framework grounded in expert correction. Such a framework must support the annotation and classification of defects as they are detected and resolved—thus enabling informed, communicable, and reproducible assessments.

2.2 Validation in 3D digitisation

It should be highlighted that the issue of such reconstruction errors can be mitigated by adopting active sensors (Pacheco et al., 2014), which are considered more precise than indirect methods, as these devices directly measure point positions in space and often implement onboard rejection of anomalous readings (Beraldin et al., 2015), reducing the likelihood of generating non-existent geometries. Consequently, apart from potential alignment inaccuracies or reflective artefacts, they are less likely to hallucinate surface features, although such methods still suffer from specific issues of their own (Huang et al., 2022).

However, such systems are often impractical in CH contexts due to limited accessibility, stemming not just from equipment and proprietary software costs (Leksell, 2018), but also from operational constraints (Wachowiak & Karas, 2009). In particular, restrictions in acquisition volume and working distance make them less flexible in the field. As a result, photogrammetric pipelines remain the preferred solution in many scenarios, despite relying on indirect reconstruction.

Hence, what matters in the context of this work is that 3D models produced through photogrammetry are, from a strictly metrological standpoint, locally uncertain. They may contain geometric features that are in fact algorithmic hallucinations, with no physical correspondence on the actual object, arising not from noise in real measurements, but from structural misinterpretation during surface estimation (Figure 3). Given these premises, metrological precision, while desirable, is not sufficient.

This intrinsic uncertainty indeed limits the effectiveness of purely numerical validation and highlights the need for interpretive frameworks that can operate within the photogrammetric pipeline itself and that are capable of identifying, classifying, and communicating the presence of surface anomalies in a structured and reproducible way.

In this light, the reliability of a photogrammetric model depends not only on the quality of its input data, but above all on the transparency of how its surface is examined, interpreted, and refined. Structured annotation of flaws conducted during expert-led correction, thus becomes a critical validation layer: more robust than global metrics, more communicable than aggregate errors, and particularly well-suited to the specific challenges of CH digitisation.

Fig. 3: The asset “Lofoforo” presenting various Surface Reconstruction hallucinations, such as the apparent holes, which are indeed the result of the thinness of the feathers, i.e. the ambiguity of the position of the points on the front and back faces. Screenshot from Zbrush.

2.3 Connectivity

Although photogrammetry workflows are increasingly consolidated, literature still focuses on isolated issues such as hole closure (Pérez et al., 2016) or filtering of noise and topological errors (Zhou et al., 2022). To the best of author’s knowledge, a comprehensive framework to identify, classify, and manage the full range of flaws, especially in CH contexts with complex geometries and suboptimal acquisition, is lacking.

This gap reflects the absence of tools specifically designed for Cultural Heritage, as most software, hardware, and algorithms are adapted from adjacent fields, such as reverse engineering (Barazzetti, 2020) and entertainment industries (Cipriani & Fantini, 2017). While the latter contribute mainly to optimisation and visual enhancement, flaw correction often relies on methods developed for man-made hard-surface objects, where geometry is simpler and boundaries clearly defined, thus favouring automated correction pipelines, where connectivity issues are fixed algorithmically.

In facts, These meshes are typically repaired using tools that operate at the level of connectivity (Sorgente et al., 2023), i.e., the structure linking vertices, edges, and polygons. Such methods are effective against high-frequency issues such as non-manifold geometry, outliers, open borders, degenerate polygons, but fail on discrete or large-scale flaws that are typical in CH assets with complex or critical surfaces, where defects may not break topological rules yet still require correction guided by semantic and morphological criteria.

2.4 Holes and algorithmic hallucinations

A relevant exception to the aforementioned considerations are holes, which are among the most studied flaws in 3D digitisation workflows and the only category to receive sustained attention in both technical and CH literature. Yet this focus remains fragmented, limited to cause classification (Nicolae et al., 2014) or procedural repairs (Pérez et al., 2016), rather than to a comprehensive analysis of their role, semantics, and treatment in CH contexts. Holes typically arise from insufficient or uneven sampling caused by occlusion, reflectance, or surface inaccessibility, and vary in shape and scale, compromising geometry, texture, or both.

Notably, the presence of holes in occluded or low-sampled regions is dependent on the algorithm used to mesh the photogrammetric point cloud. Poisson reconstruction and depth map–based fusion methods do not

generate holes, as they return closed or contiguous surfaces, even if this is accomplished by patching poorly sampled areas with low-confidence interpolated geometry. Nonetheless, these patches are often removed during post-processing, and the resulting absence of geometry produces the same topological condition as a hole—albeit with different semantic implications.

Algorithmic hallucinations, similarly, when not corrected through deformation while preserving mesh connectivity, are commonly removed once identified, thus recreating the same topological condition reported for patch removal. Yet their identification is not straightforward, as geometry remains continuous while exhibiting localised distortions, morphological, cumulative, or patterned, that alter form without generating missing data. Consequently, these artefacts often escape immediate detection, despite their impact on visual plausibility and metric reliability.

In practice, many such flaws are well known to experienced operators, who recognise them empirically in the course of established correction routines. However, these insights rarely translate into formal classifications. Issues such as insufficient sampling in high-curvature regions, surface bridging, photometric misinterpretation, or local shading artefacts are widespread, yet typically fall outside structured analysis frameworks or are absorbed into global quality metrics (Remondino et al., 2017).

This reveals a persistent disconnection between operational knowledge and theoretical formalisation. Without explicit characterisation, the legitimacy of correcting such flaws remains ambiguous, and their documentation is often neglected. By embedding both semantic segmentation and correlation with mesh analysis indicators within the correction process, the present framework aims to convert situated expertise into structured descriptions, enabling the emergence of a consistent, empirically grounded taxonomy.

3. Mesh Analysis Indicators

3.1 Frequency

Flaws, like all surface morphologies, may manifest at different spatial scales. At large scale, they affect the overall geometry, altering global shape and structural continuity; at small scale, they produce local irregularities, surface noise, or microgeometric distortions.

In mesh processing, this variation is commonly interpreted through the notion of frequency, a concept derived from signal theory and formalised via spectral analysis tools (Zhang et al., 2007) that decompose surface variation by scale, supporting operations such as smoothing, simplification, or feature-aware filtering, and enabling a multiscale reading of geometric behaviour.

In the present framework, frequency is used in a qualitative sense to articulate both the behaviour of the geometric indicators introduced in the following section and the morphology of defects. It also underpins the proposed flaw taxonomy, where defects are grouped by their dominant spatial frequency.

3.2 Curvature and its proxies

Although frequency-based analysis operates on the 2D manifold of the mesh, the surface itself is embedded in 3D space, where its local shape is governed by geometric quantities such as curvature, or more precisely, by its discrete approximation suitable for non-continuous polygonal surfaces. In fact, curvature is formally defined within the framework of differential geometry, which assumes instead smooth and continuous surfaces and where it is a local property derived from surface normals and second-order derivatives. The curvature of a surface varies depending on the direction along which it is evaluated; hence, the most relevant quantities are the principal curvatures, that is, the maximum and minimum values at each point. Notably, their corresponding directions are orthogonal and provide an effective description of local surface behaviour.

But when a surface is represented as a polygonal mesh, differential tools are no longer directly applicable. A first remedy consists in local surface fitting, which enables the application of differential analysis on a fitted continuous surface such as quadrics (Cipriano et al., 2009) or a osculating jets (Cazals & Pouget, 2005) within a fixed radius. An alternative instead uses advanced tools adapted to discrete settings, such as discrete shape operators and the cotangent Laplacian (Meyer et al., 2003), but while formally accurate, these are

computationally demanding and not natively supported in CH digitisation software like MeshLab or CloudCompare.

For morphological purposes, however, proper curvature is often less relevant than curvature variation across a neighbourhood, which can be captured by compact descriptors. These descriptors, and especially their distribution across the surface, support the identification of salient geometric features at different spatial frequencies, so that by analysing how shape-related quantities vary at increasing scales, it becomes possible to distinguish low-frequency deformations from high-frequency details. Such multiscale morphometric descriptors are widely used in mesh analysis, feature extraction, remeshing, and feature-driven smoothing.

A common approach to extract such descriptors is Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (Jolliffe & Cadima, 2016), which provides robust indicators of shape variation and is both well-established and computationally accessible. At each vertex, PCA computes the covariance matrix of a fixed-radius neighbourhood. The eigenvectors of this matrix approximate the local directions of maximal, intermediate, and minimal spatial variance, while the corresponding eigenvalues quantify the extent of variation along these directions. In regular regions and under dense sampling, the direction of minimal variance tends to align with the local normal, while the other two span the tangent plane and approximate the principal curvature directions. In the limit case of infinitesimal radius and infinitely dense sampling, this decomposition converges to the differential frame defined by the surface normal and the principal directions of curvature.

Moreover, PCA acts as a low-pass approximation of curvature-like behaviour near the kernel scale, so that surface features with lower spatial frequencies are effectively suppressed, making PCA sensitive only to variation within the kernel's resolution, as the resulting eigenstructure encodes the smoothed geometric behaviour of the surface at that scale. In a multiscale framework, this becomes an asset rather than a limitation, as it enables the extraction of curvature-like descriptors that reflect the latent morphology of the object across different levels of detail. Scalar indicators derived from PCA, such as planarity, sphericity, or anisotropy, provide robust, noise-tolerant and multiscale cues for morphological classification, and are therefore adopted for the analysis of the mesh portions segmented as flaws. Among the available PCA-derived descriptors, two are systematically employed in this framework.

- *Omnivariance*: computed as the cubic root of the product of the three eigenvalues of the local covariance matrix, captures the overall magnitude of spatial variation and serves as a key indicator of morphological deviation.
- *Linearity*: computed from the relative dominance of the first eigenvalue, reflects the directional character of that variation. This distinction is particularly relevant for differentiating point-like features (e.g., spikes or pits) from elongated anomalies (e.g., ridges or bridging). Both indicators are computed at multiple scales to enhance robustness and support the frequency-based reading of surface flaws introduced in the taxonomy.

The associated scalar fields can be visualised as false-colour maps in tools like CloudCompare (Figure 4), enabling both qualitative evaluation and quantitative use. Although their values are not metrologically absolute, they offer a reproducible morphometric substrate that supports interpretation and documentation. Crucially, they allow operators to distinguish between plausible features and suspect anomalies based on local variation patterns.

Though this estimation remains approximate, it offers a consistent and operationally viable method grounded in mesh geometry. Its aim is not to replace expert judgement, but to reinforce it by providing localised, reproducible metrics that support interpretation. These indicators may also serve as anchors for future workflows, including machine-learning-based flaw detection and multiscale segmentation.

Fig. 4: Zoomed colour-mapped visualisation of a PCA-based indicator (*Omnivariance*) scalar field in *CloudCompare*, computed for the RAWp asset “*Lophius Piscatorius*”. The wireframe overlay enables simultaneous visual evaluation of the *Edge Length* indicator and highlights plausible flaws in regions where low omnivariance (blue)—at the given analysis scale—correlates with relatively long edges.

3.3 Metrological Indicators

The scalar fields described above offer robust support for characterising surface morphology by capturing geometric traits across different spatial frequencies. However, these indicators remain agnostic to the origin of such variations: a sharp deviation may equally correspond to a legitimate feature or a reconstruction flaw.

To reduce this ambiguity, morphometric descriptors are complemented by metrological indicators, which help qualify the plausibility of surface patterns and guide the interpretation of potentially flawed regions. These measures provide contextual information about the acquisition process, contributing to the assessment of structural reliability in the reconstructed mesh. Specifically, the metrological indicators adopted are local sampling density, operationalised as *Edge Length*, and photogrammetric *Confidence* scores.

Among the available metrological cues, average *Edge Length*, as a proxy for acquisition sampling, plays a key role in the emergence and visibility of flaws. While smooth regions may be well described even at low densities, areas with high curvature or complex features require denser and more structured sampling: when the local density is insufficient to resolve features at a given spatial frequency, reconstruction fails to capture them accurately. In fact, a feature of scale d must be sampled with spacing smaller than $d/2$ in order to be reconstructed as geometry rather than noise, as stated by the Nyquist–Shannon theorem. This condition is often unmet in real-world acquisitions, especially in occluded or critical regions.

Confidence refers to a scalar field assigned to each vertex or face, as implemented in commonly used photogrammetric software. It reflects the stability of the reconstruction process rather than a geometric property, and is typically estimated from factors such as image coverage, angular redundancy, and depth consistency. Although confidence is derived from internal reconstruction parameters, it does not directly measure the geometric accuracy of the resulting model: while low-confidence areas often correspond to occlusions, poor sampling, or suboptimal viewing angles, conditions that also lead to frequent reconstruction flaws, high-confidence regions, despite being well supported by the dataset, do not alone guarantee accuracy, as systematic errors such as poor photometric quality, repeated textures, or alignment faults can still produce flaws in geometrically stable areas.

In this work, confidence is therefore not used as a primary classification axis but as a supporting parameter that helps anticipate unreliability. It provides a qualitative indication of regions requiring manual or automatic review. In future developments, confidence may be used for uncertainty segmentation or as an input feature

for training data-driven classification models. Together, morphometric and metrological indicators offer a descriptive substrate for characterising mesh flaws. Building upon this framework, we introduce a methodology that formalises flaw recognition through a structured taxonomy.

4. Methodology

4.1 Epistemological aspects

In photogrammetric workflows, correction is often treated as a neutral post-processing step. However, in Cultural Heritage digitisation, where shape plausibility is context-dependent and reconstruction flaws may resemble legitimate features, correction becomes an interpretive act, as the decision to intervene implies a judgment about what should or should not be present. Each correction thus encodes an implicit classification: it isolates a flawed region, delimits its extent, and modifies or reconstructs it according to an internal plausibility model informed by domain knowledge, visual inspection, and contextual cues.

Rather than preceding correction, flaw recognition typically emerges through it. The operator may begin without a complete map of defects, progressively identifying anomalies as familiarity with the model increases. This process relies not only on geometry, but also on texture analysis, as chromatic deformations, background leakage, or projection inconsistencies often signal problematic regions even before geometric inspection. Crucially, this evaluation is intrinsically binary: a surface is either accepted or modified. At scale, these discrete decisions define a de facto segmentation of the model into reliable and flawed regions.

This non-intrusive configuration is essential. The framework does not alter operator behaviour but retrospectively captures decisions already enacted, ensuring that classification emerges from actual expert practice rather than from prescriptive modelling. It functions as an epistemic observer that, rather than prescribing correction, retroactively structures the interpretive decisions made by the operator, transforming them into a traceable semantic layer, since each intervention embeds a prior diagnosis of local plausibility, albeit non-formalised. Once segmented and projected back onto the unedited model, these corrections can be analytically interpreted through mesh-based indicators such as curvature, sampling density, and reconstruction confidence, which provide geometric support without constraining operator evaluation.

As segmentation becomes available, it becomes possible to investigate whether recurring patterns emerge in the combination of geometric and morphometric indicators associated with corrected regions. If such patterns prove consistent, they may serve as proxies for flaw recognition, allowing this crucial judgment, currently performed by the human operator, to be progressively automated.

Nonetheless, classification remains retrospective at the current stage, emerging from corrected outputs. This feedback configuration is not structurally required by the method but constitutes a transitional strategy for formalising tacit knowledge. Only once a robust taxonomy is established, flaws may be directly tagged at the point of recognition, allowing the system to evolve from a descriptive tool into a diagnostic and predictive framework.

4.2 Dataset

The development of the proposed method was informed by empirical observations conducted on two separate datasets, both derived from recent digitisation campaigns involving heterogeneous Cultural Heritage collections. The first dataset includes naturalistic specimens originally displayed in a temporary exhibition dedicated to early modern scientific collections. The second consists mainly of paleontological and geological items housed in a historical university museum.

Both datasets were selected as pilot cases due to their diversity in scale, material, morphology, and acquisition context. Combined, they include taxidermied animals, fossils, wax models, numismatic items, decorated surfaces, printed volumes, xylographic plates, and archaeological artefacts, offering a broad representation of tangible heritage typologies and associated digitisation challenges. Institutional references have been anonymised for review purposes and will be reinstated in the final version.

The models were generated through standard SfM/MVS pipelines and manually processed by various operators, including the author. During this processing, particularly in the cleaning and optimisation phases, recurrent geometric issues were encountered, prompting the identification of flaw patterns that later informed the structure of the proposed taxonomy. A subset of assets handled directly by the author was retrospectively examined using this emerging interpretive framework. These models were not selected to "test" the method, but rather became part of the iterative process through which it was conceived. Other assets, although processed with different workflows and objectives, contributed to defining the broader operational context in which flaw types and frequency patterns were recognised.

The taxonomy, therefore, was not applied across the dataset as a finished diagnostic tool, but rather derived inductively from selected segments of practice. It remains non-validated in inter-operator terms and has not yet been used to annotate the dataset in a systematic way. Nonetheless, the corpus provided a grounded empirical substrate for articulating preliminary morphological classes and diagnostic frequencies. The classification should thus be interpreted as a provisional structuring of expert insight, not as the result of a completed validation protocol.

This initial formalisation, by explicitly encoding practitioner experience into a reproducible structure, now enables the possibility of systematic verification. A future intra-operator application, built upon the present conceptual groundwork, may serve to consolidate the taxonomy and flaw characterisation, while also potentially transforming them through extended and comparative implementation. Such a follow-up study would represent a necessary step towards assessing internal coherence, operator consistency, and diagnostic utility within controlled use cases.

4.3 Automatic filtering in RAWp

As outlined in Section 1.2, the present method integrates with the RAW - DCHO pipeline, specifically at the transition from RAWp to DCHO, maintaining its structure and intent. The crucial distinction, preserved here, is that DCHO includes all critical, authorial corrections addressing complex flaws that cannot be resolved through automated filtering, of which RAWp is the final output.

Indeed, RAWp is not the raw mesh, but a preprocessed version derived through automated procedures aimed at removing well-characterised connectivity defects such as outliers, noise, non-manifold elements, degenerate polygons, self-intersections, anisotropies, or inconsistent normal orientation, as extensively discussed in (Sorgente et al., 2023). These issues are typically addressed through deterministic or AI-based approaches, many of which are embedded in standard mesh-cleaning tools commonly used in digitisation workflows.

4.4 Tracing interventions in DCHO

Having clarified the role of RAWp and anticipated that the operations leading to DCHO are critical and authorial in nature, it follows that correction is not a neutral refinement but a privileged moment of interpretive decision. The operator identifies surface anomalies and applies remedial actions, such as sculpting, re-modelling, deletion and reconstruction. These interventions have a primarily operational function, aimed at improving mesh quality, but at the same time, they carry epistemic value, as by establishing what requires correction, they implicitly define what is considered defective and help delineate the boundaries for classification.

To support this process, the method implements a variation of the active tracing mechanism embedded in the DCHO phase outlined in Blinded for Review (2), with the difference that the tracing deploys polygon groups instead of vertex color maps (Figure 5). As corrections are performed, the mesh is segmented using a standardised set of semantic categories, which describe the nature of the intervention applied rather than the specific tool or technique:

- *Hole-filling*: Address regions where photogrammetric interpolation is unreliable, typically contiguous zones with low confidence and anomalous edge length, but are surrounded by consistent geometry. These areas are manually removed to expose the underlying gap, which is then manually filled by inferring the missing geometry by adjacent topology and comparison with the raw photographic dataset.

- *Sculpting or morphological adjustment*: Corrects surface anomalies by altering the morphology without altering mesh connectivity.
- *Insertion or reconstruction of geometry*: Is reserved for regions where no reliable geometry can be recovered. In these cases, the photogrammetric model serves only as a general reference, and new geometry is directly modelled to restore the intended form. Examples include reflective or translucent surfaces, or fragmented structures such as pearl strings.
- *Surface smoothing*: Addresses high-frequency noise or residual microgeometry. It is applied over larger areas but does not lend itself to discrete segmentation, and is therefore treated as a diffuse, untagged intervention.

This segmentation is recorded manually, with the operator defining boundaries and assigning labels. While tools and techniques may vary, annotation should conform to the defined categories to ensure semantic consistency across interventions.

Fig. 5: Coloured segments differentiate operator interventions on the asset "Sid". Pink segments correspond to occluded areas whose geometry had been reconstructed with consistent geometry using topological guides; violet segments are related to hole-filling; the orange segment reflects only minor localised smoothing. The editing technique is reported here as an example of the corrections tracing, although its implementation falls outside the scope of the present work. Screenshot from ZBrush.

4.5 Retroprojection of segments to RAWp

From a technical standpoint, corrections modify the RAWp mesh, sometimes subtly, as in smoothing operations, and sometimes radically, through sculpting or replacement of geometry. Areas deemed reliable are typically left untouched or gently regularised to remove residual noise. As a result, DCHO is not topologically or morphologically identical to RAWp.

This difference can be exploited. The method described here applies a retroprojection process, in which segments defined in DCHO are spatially mapped back onto RAWp via raycasting modulated by geometric proximity (Blinded for review, 3). This operation, referred to here as retroprojection, identifies on RAWp the regions that have been altered in DCHO, thereby exposing the areas that were implicitly recognised as flawed and subjected to correction (Figure 6). The procedure is not intended to provide accurate pointwise correspondence between RAWp and DCHO, but to produce a workable approximation of corrected zones on the unedited mesh.

This enables RAWp to be geometrically segmented based on the local corrections applied in DCHO. However, this backward detection acquires a different meaning within RAWp: here, the segments do not reflect corrections, but rather identify the flaws themselves, established as such precisely because they were corrected, thus transforming RAWp into a diagnostic surface marked by operator-recognised anomalies.

These segments can then be analysed in conjunction with mesh indicators, curvature, edge length, confidence, to characterise each region in both morphological and procedural terms. Retroprojection establishes the knowledge loop that grounds classification in real-world operations, elevating RAWp from passive product of automated processing to epistemic layer: a representation of the object that includes not only artefacts, but the operator's recognition of them.

Technically auxiliary, this step is methodologically central during the exploratory phase. It enables the systematisation of tacit recognition, providing a structured bridge between correction and classification. In future stages, when flaws are analytically defined and directly taggable, retroprojection may no longer be required. But in the current configuration, it plays a foundational role in turning embodied knowledge into communicable structure.

Yet retroprojection introduces a structural vulnerability, as annotations are made during correction, but classification of flaws occurs afterwards, once the original interpretive act has already taken place. The retroprojection is therefore temporally and semantically detached from its source. Spatial correspondence may be imprecise, and categories inferred a posteriori may not fully reflect the rationale behind each correction. These shifts, both geometric and interpretive, may distort the intended meaning of the correction and lead to inconsistencies in flaw classification.

Crucially, this feedback mechanism is explicitly provisional. Its purpose is not to ensure perfect segment alignment, but to support the foundational phase in which flaw types are defined, validated, and normalised. The immediate priority is to surface, name, and structure recurring defect patterns. Consequently, minor inconsistencies are tolerated, as they do not compromise the emergence of robust categories. Once the taxonomy is established and internalised, segmentation will occur directly on RAWp, enabling a consistent propagation of semantically meaningful regions throughout the workflow. The fragility of the current feedback process is thus a necessary condition of its foundational role, and its obsolescence is already embedded in the method's own trajectory.

Fig. 6: Retroprojection from DCHO to RAWp enables the segmentation of flaws based on past corrections, leading to the emergence of flaw types. This feedback loop functions as a device for extracting and structuring tacit knowledge.

4.6 Application of Mesh Analysis in the Method.

Within the proposed framework, mesh analysis refers to the interpretation of morphometric and metrological indicators extracted from the RAWp model. Its function is not to certify accuracy, but to assist in the local inspection of surface behaviour, supporting flaw identification through patterns such as curvature anomalies, irregular edge length, or low-confidence regions. None of these descriptors is diagnostic in isolation: a sharp curvature anomaly, for example, may reflect either a legitimate feature or a reconstruction artefact.

PCA-derived indicators are not used as standalone classifiers but as morphological guides. They are combined with metrologically grounded descriptors to disambiguate similar geometric patterns. This composite approach consolidates qualitative expertise with structural evidence, facilitating reproducible interpretation and laying the groundwork for future semi-automated classification. As detailed in Sections 3.2 and 3.3, four indicators are employed:

- *Omnivariance:* Is used to locate zones of marked deviation from surface regularity and to differentiate between broad anomalies and fine-grained artefacts across multiple scales.
- *Linearity:* Supports the morphological reading of the deviation by helping to distinguish point-like artefacts from elongated or directional features.
- *Edge Length:* Is assessed through wireframe inspection to identify locally undersampled or degenerate regions where instability or detail loss may occur.
- *Confidence:* Is used to flag areas where reconstruction plausibility is low and operator intervention more likely, even if is not a geometric descriptor,

PCA indicators are currently visualised using tools such as MeshLab or CloudCompare and interpreted qualitatively to support segmentation, while edge length is not computed as a scalar field but is assessed visually through the mesh wireframe, which offers an immediate and interpretable cue about local sampling

structure. This visual inspection remains consistent with the expert-driven diagnostic strategy adopted throughout the method and could be formalised in future implementations using automated edge metrics, such as a proper multiscale *Mean Edge Length* metric.

As discussed in 4.5, flaw-related segments are identified retrospectively and subsequently characterised through a combined reading of local patterns and morphological appearance. As the taxonomy becomes established, this phase will shift toward analytical classification grounded in thresholds and indicator combinations. Mesh analysis will thus evolve from an interpretive aid into a structural component of a reproducible diagnostic layer, and descriptors may be embedded directly as vertex attributes or used externally as auxiliary data layers, depending on implementation. This modularity enables integration into different segmentation or classification pipelines without altering the mesh structure.

4.7 Semantic Structuring and Paradata Integration

While not implemented in the present study, the segments derived from correction and flaw recognition are inherently semantic. As discussed in Section 4.1, segmentation applied to 3D models is never purely geometric: it encodes interpretive choices made during correction on DCHO, namely paradata, and provides the foundation for plausibility assessment of reconstructed areas on RAWp, in line with the London Charter (2009). This semantic layer permeates the entire methodological framework and lies at the core of the problem outlined in Sections 1 and 1.1, which this work aims to address through a structured approach.

This raises a key question: how can the embedded semantic information in DCHO and RAWp be interfaced with external metadata ontologies? Unlike external annotation models based on separate property files, the approach proposed here embeds semantic content directly within the 3D model. Two hypothetical strategies can be envisioned, both easily implementable without altering the method. The first, more lightweight, encodes meaning directly into the segment name. Each layer is assigned a UID (Unique Identifier) that includes the flaw or correction type and an alphanumeric code, allowing for both human readability and automated parsing. The second, more articulated, involves associating structured metadata with each segment—for instance, typological class, frequency band, confidence level, or editing rationale—using custom property containers available in environments such as Blender. These attributes could then be retrieved by custom parsers or upon import into external systems. This would allow more expressive metadata to be embedded within the file itself, without relying on external descriptors, and would facilitate future alignment with ontologies or machine-readable interfaces.

These hypothetical strategies aim to explore the feasibility of embedding semantically structured information within 3D assets. While their full implementation exceeds the scope of this article, they are conceptually aligned with current efforts to encode geometric semantics through CIDOC CRM extensions (Giovannini, 2018; (Amico & Felicetti, 2021), even if such approaches are typically tailored to architectural-scale models rather than object-scale artefacts.

What is particularly relevant to the present work is that both the cleaned mesh (DCHO) and the flaw-tagged version (RAWp) are already understood as dual-purpose artefacts: not only geometric representations, but also carriers of structured, interpretable paradata. Together, these layers define a stable and differentiated information system within the RAW → DCHO workflow, where each mesh state is not merely a procedural step but a semantically meaningful unit of knowledge.

5. Taxonomy

5.1 General rationale

The taxonomy presented here stems from a first operational implementation of the method, directly applied by the author within real-world digitisation workflows, as recalled in 4.2. It reflects qualitative knowledge consolidated through repeated mesh correction tasks and should be understood as a preliminary articulation of classification logic, internally coherent but not yet externally validated. As defined in the methodology, flaw types have been derived retrospectively from expert-guided correction, then annotated and grouped based on recurring morphological patterns, spatial scale, and indicative mesh metrics.

Although grounded in general geometric principles, the taxonomy is inevitably influenced by the specific surface reconstruction algorithms used. Different strategies, such as Poisson reconstruction, Delaunay triangulation, or Marching Cubes, tend to produce distinct families of artefacts and modulate their appearance. For instance, Poisson reconstruction generates watertight surfaces by design and never leaves open holes, while Delaunay or Marching Cubes may result in incomplete or disconnected regions. A flaw may therefore appear differently or even not at all, depending on the reconstruction pipeline. In this implementation, the taxonomy is primarily informed by Depth Map fusion workflows, as consistently adopted across all test assets. However, it is deliberately structured to accommodate outputs from other reconstruction paradigms, ensuring adaptability across heterogeneous datasets and use cases.

While this version is based on a single-operator corpus, its goal is not to impose a fixed classification, but to demonstrate how semantic segmentation can emerge from procedural traceability and domain-specific judgement. It serves as a proof of concept: a foundational set of flaw types derived through structured intervention tracing and retroprojection. Although sufficiently mature to support analytical reflection, the taxonomy remains provisional. Broader adoption will require systematic application across diverse digitisation contexts by independent operators, within a future validation programme.

5.2 Characterisation of flaws

As flaw classification in the current framework follows the intervention based on the retroprojected mapping of corrected areas onto RAWp, there is a structural risk that categories may be shaped by the techniques used to correct them. To prevent this, the taxonomy has been deliberately constructed to remain independent of specific remediation strategies. Rather than deriving flaw types from the nature of the intervention, it defines them through observable morphological traits and recurring causal patterns. Correction strategies may align with these categories, but they do not determine them.

This separation is essential to avoid any circular reasoning in which the classification of a flaw would merely reflect the technique used to correct it. By defining flaws independently of remediation strategies, the taxonomy promotes an objective understanding of mesh defects and preserves its applicability across different tools, workflows, and software ecosystems. It also prevents premature assumptions about optimal correction, which may vary by context or evolve with technological progress.

Each flaw entry in the taxonomy follows a consistent template structured into three sections:

- *Visual example*: a representative image drawn from the annotated dataset, showing a real-world occurrence of the flaw. For conciseness and to avoid redundancy, only three illustrative examples are included in this publication.
- *Morphological description*: a concise qualitative account of the flaw's appearance, typical geometric configuration, and recurrent locations on the mesh (e.g., tips, folds, recesses). Terminology is chosen to remain scientifically grounded while accessible to non-specialist users. Where no established label existed in the literature, new names were introduced following the same communicative intent.
- *Morfometric analysis*: a qualitative reading of how the flaw correlates with mesh indicators—*Photogrammetric Confidence*, visually assessed *Edge Length*, and two PCA-derived descriptors (*Omnivariance* and *Linearity*). As discussed in Section 4.3, these indicators support operator recognition but are not used as classification criteria. Their interpretation relies on visualisation through false-colour maps and wireframes.

It is important to point out that PCA is known to be unstable when applied to sparsely sampled areas, due to the limited number of vertices within the analysis kernel (Pauly et al., 2003). This issue is particularly relevant for photogrammetric meshes, which are typically non-isotropic. To mitigate this weakness at an operational level, the mesh can be densified (Jaiswal et al., 2024); in the current implementation, this is achieved by resampling the entire mesh so that large polygons are populated with additional points, thereby improving the stability of the PCA computation.

Moreover, PCA-derived indicators provide stable and interpretable proxies for local surface variation, but lack directional information, as the eigenvalues of a covariance matrix are inherently positive. As a result, these descriptors cannot distinguish between convex and concave regions. Yet for a human operator, this distinction is both immediate and decisive: a cusp and a pit, or a ridge and a fold, are perceived as fundamentally different.

This gap highlights the descriptive limits of scalar indicators when decoupled from embodied recognition. Hence, such distinctions are consistently reflected in the flaw categories and differentiated mainly via morphological description. In future iterations, they may be formalised analytically through more expressive mesh analysis and integrated into semi-automated pre-assessment workflows. The proposed classification should therefore be understood as a first operational implementation, structured to accommodate future refinements.

5.3 Differentiation in LOW, MID, HIGH-Frequency

The classification of flaws in this taxonomy is primarily organised by the spatial scale at which they manifest, as introduced in Section 3.1. Coherently, PCA descriptors are computed at three neighbourhood scales using kernels of appropriate size. Rather than linking each indicator to a specific frequency band, the analysis evaluates local surface behaviour across all scales. This multiscale comparison supports the identification of flaws by detecting patterns both at individual frequencies and across the full spectrum.

To enable comparison across objects of different sizes, a relative measure of spatial frequency is adopted, defined as $\lambda^{-1} = D / d$, where D is the characteristic size of the object (e.g., the bounding box diagonal), and d is the estimated extent of the flaw—understood as the region over which the geometric irregularity is visibly expressed.

This formulation does not rely on absolute thresholds, but instead relates flaw size to object scale. For example, a spike of fixed dimension may appear negligible on a large object or as a major deformation on a small one. The parameter λ^{-1} captures this proportionality, allowing classification based on perceptual and morphological salience rather than absolute metrics.

In practice, d is not derived from mesh primitives such as triangle width or edge length, but corresponds to a qualitative footprint estimated by the operator—e.g., the diameter of a bulge, the radius of a void, or the length of a fold. While based on expert judgment, this estimate is grounded in visual and structural cues. Future refinement using curvature fields, confidence maps, or error metrics is anticipated but not implemented here.

Based on λ^{-1} , three empirical bands are defined: LOW frequency ($\lambda^{-1} < 5$), MID frequency ($5 \leq \lambda^{-1} \leq 10$), and HIGH frequency ($\lambda^{-1} > 20$). Intermediate values ($10 < \lambda^{-1} \leq 20$) are treated as transitional and assigned based on dominant morphology. These bands are heuristic and non-predictive; they serve to support operator-level recognition and enable comparative classification. Some flaws may span multiple bands, but each is assigned to the frequency where it most typically occurs in the analysed corpus.

To reduce redundancy and improve readability, the bands are abbreviated as LF (Low Frequency), MF (Mid Frequency), and HF (High Frequency) throughout flaw descriptions. These designations indicate the scale at which each indicator—particularly Omnivariance—is evaluated within the multiscale PCA analysis.

Finally, many high-frequency flaws commonly recognised in the literature, such as noise, spikes, and mesh connectivity errors, are not included in this taxonomy, as they are systematically filtered out during the automatic processing leading to RAWp (see Section 4.3). These artefacts are typically morphologically degenerate rather than ambiguous and thus require no further differentiation within this framework.

5.4 Flaw Taxonomy

5.2.1 Low-Frequency Flaws

F_L_PAT; LOW-CONFIDENCE PATCH

Smooth areas that appear geometrically plausible but exhibit a visibly higher frequency than their surroundings, often through edge interpolation. While such flaws correspond to actual holes in some reconstruction pipelines, in DM workflows they manifest as subtly inflated closures or false continuities, frequently aligned with low-visibility or photometrically challenging zones.

- *Confidence*: Low with a smooth gradient at the boundary.
- *EdgeLength*: High, increasing with the size of the anomaly.
- *Omnivariance*: Low and locally smooth, with limited internal variation.

- *Linearity*: Weak and diffuse, with no dominant directionality.

F_M_BLO; GLANCING ANGLE BLOBS

Irregular swollen growths, often asymmetrical and detached from the underlying morphological logic of the item and extend outward from the expected surface envelope, typically along edges or tips of the object. Correlated to dataset images showing the item against a contrasting background.

- *Confidence*: Low or uneven across the affected protrusion.
- *EdgeLength*: Longer than the surrounding area, isotropic over the anomaly.
- *Omnivariance*: Low at LF and MF, moderate HF near the protrusion's border.
- *Linearity*: High, aligned with the edge tangent.

F_L_CEM; CONNECTION MEMBRANES

These artefacts appear smooth and continuous, often planar or twisted, and typically resemble thin membranes stretched between two structural anchor curves. They occur between folds, cavities, or opposed surfaces, and are often located in narrow voids or connecting opposed low-sampled surfaces.

- *Confidence*: Low, with short gradient at the boundary
- *EdgeLength*: Low.
- *Omnivariance*: Generally low, with localised HF peaks along boundaries.
- *Linearity*: Low, with directional spikes near boundaries.

Fig. 7: Zbrush postprocessed screenshots showing examples of Low-frequency flaws: Membrane Bridges *F_L_MEM* (left) in the “Limulo” asset; Glancing Angle Blobs *F_L_BLO* (mid) in the “Sid” asset; Low-Confidence Patch *F_L_PAT* (right) in the “Sardo” asset.

5.2.2 Mid-Frequency Flaws

F_M_ISL; HIGH SAMPLING ISLANDS

Localised areas of detailed geometry embedded in otherwise smooth, low-curvature surfaces. These patches exhibit coherent polarity with their surroundings but disrupt visual continuity, appearing as dense mesostructures within homogeneous regions. Often correlated with photometric anomalies, such as high-contrast zones within otherwise uniform textures.

- *Confidence*: High, consistent with the surrounding surface.
- *EdgeLength*: Significantly shorter than neighbouring regions.
- *Omnivariance*: Low at LF and MF; moderate HF within the island.
- *Linearity*: Nearly null with no consistent directional structure.

F_M_GHO; REFLECTION GHOSTS

Detached or floating geometries, often semi-coherent but visibly disconnected. These artefacts may mimic nearby features in distorted form or appear as duplicated, misaligned volumes hovering over the surface. Correlated to image sets with flat reflective surfaces.

- *Confidence*: Variable, but generally low.
- *EdgeLength*: Mostly short, but uneven.
- *Omnivariance*: Variable and non-characteristic, ranging from low to high depending on local structure.
- *Linearity*: Variable, with localised directionality emerging in elongated fragments.

F_M_BLU; TIP BLUNTING

Rounded or truncated terminations of pointed features. These areas lose their sharp angular profile, replaced by domed or flattened ends and are shortened in respect to the real item. The entity of blunting is inversely proportional to sampling.

- *Confidence*: High and comparable to the neighborhood.
- *EdgeLength*: Slightly longer than the neighborhood.
- *Omnivariance*: Low, with smoothed HF variation near the tip.
- *Linearity*: Locally variable, moderate along the preserved axis but low at the blunted tip.

F_M_FIL; PIT FILLING

Depressions or cavities that appear shallower than expected or completely filled in, resulting in the loss or flattening of concave features. The mesh forms a smooth convex or planar patch, obscuring the original indentation.

- *Confidence*: Comparable to the surrounding surface.
- *EdgeLength*: Slightly longer within the filled patch.
- *Omnivariance*: Low at LF and MF; locally increased HF near the edge of the filled area.
- *Linearity*: Low and incoherent across the flattened surface.

F_M_ATT; CRESTS ATTENUATION

Linear features such as ridges, folds, or sharp edges appear softened or rounded, losing their sharp definition. The crest becomes thicker and less distinct, occasionally bloated, with reduced contrast across adjacent surface orientations.

- *Confidence*: Comparable to the surrounding surface.
- *EdgeLength*: Slightly longer across the smoothed transition.
- *Omnivariance*: Low at LF and MF; moderate HF response near inflection points.
- *Linearity*: Moderate along the crest, decreasing in smoothed regions

F_M_SHA; CREVICES SHALLOWING

Narrow grooves or fissures that appear partially filled, resulting in an often irregular but generally shallower geometry on the bottom of the crevice. The original separation between adjacent features is lost, and the geometry is smoothed in areas where a clear incision should be present.

- *Confidence*: High, with irregular drop near the former groove;
- *EdgeLength*: Short, but inconsistent in directionality and depth;
- *Omnivariance*: Low at LF and MF, moderate HF where local shape breaks occur;
- *Linearity*: Weak and unstable along the expected groove axis.

F_M_SKI; DOUBLE SKIN

Duplicated, sheet-like surface layers running near and roughly parallel to the actual geometry, forming thin offset shells on low curvature geometry. These artefacts may be continuous or fragmented and tend to follow the real surface with slight misalignment. The corresponding area of the true geometry is often less resolved.

- *Confidence*: Moderate to high, decreasing towards the duplicated layer's boundaries.
- *EdgeLength*: Slightly shorter within the duplicated region; longer on the underlying surface.
- *Omnivariance*: Low at LF and MF, with scattered HF anomalies along overlaps.
- *Linearity*: Moderate, aligned with the curvature direction of the true surface.

F_M_MEM; COLLAPSED MEMBRANES

Localised collapse of very thin structures. They do not resolve the expected separation between layers, resulting in missing geometry and creating additional non-existing holes, in the topological sense, whose perimeter is formed by high curvature junctions between opposite sides of the structure.

- *Confidence*: Even with neighborhood, suddenly increased for the junctions.
- *EdgeLength*: Generally short and even with surroundings, also in the junctions due to thinness.
- *Omnivariance*: Low at LF, with irregular spikes at MF and HF near topological disruptions.
- *Linearity*: Locally high along the junction at HF.

F_M_CAV; SPECULAR CAVITIES

Isolated or clustered depressions appearing like irregular corruptions, misaligned with actual geometry and located in areas affected by strong specular highlights, especially if homogeneously coloured. They have smooth edges and shallow depth, disrupting otherwise continuous, flat or low-curvature surfaces.

- *Confidence*: Moderate, often inconsistent with surrounding surface.
- *EdgeLength*: Regular but elongated in the cavity
- *Omnivariance*: Low at LF, locally increased at MF around contour.
- *Linearity*: Low, with low directionality at the border.

Fig. 8: Zbrush postprocessed screenshots showing examples of Mid-frequency flaws: *Specular Cavities F_M_SPC* (left) in the “Kung” asset; *Crevices Shallowing F_M_SHA* (Mid) in the “Lophius” asset; *Collapsed Membranes F_M_COM* (right) in the “Lofoforo” asset.

5.2.3 High-Frequency Flaws

F_H_PEA; STRING OF PEARLS

Elongated features appear fragmented into rounded, bead-like segments separated by gaps or depressions. The artefact disrupts linear continuity, especially in thin ridges or filaments, producing an alternation of swollen nodes and voids.

- *Confidence*: High, homogeneous along the structure.
- *EdgeLength*: Locally short, alternating with slightly longer gaps.

- *Omnivariance*: Low at LF, locally moderate at MF and high at HF around bead edges.
- *Linearity*: Alternating; low within each bead, higher in segments connecting them.

F_H_TEX; TEXTURE-INDUCED MICROGEOMETRY

Fine-scale surface artefacts that replicate texture patterns rather than true geometry. They appear as low-relief ridges, dots, or grain aligned with photometric structures—e.g., brush strokes, veins, or prints—over otherwise smooth or weakly curved regions.

- *Confidence*: High, consistent with surrounding surface.
- *EdgeLength*: Shorter than average, uniformly distributed.
- *Omnivariance*: Low at LF and MF, moderate HF where false details emerge.
- *Linearity*: Weak, scattered and locally directional if texture is structured.

F_H_CRU; OFFSET CRUST

Plausible surface patches slightly offset from the true geometry, often hard to detect centrally but producing visible steps along their boundary and presenting irregular corroded margins, then small islands emerging with constant offset around the proper margin. Typically localised on low curvature areas. This type may subsume seam-like artefacts in active-sensor workflows.

- *Confidence*: High on the crust, drop-offs near its borders might be present.
- *EdgeLength*: Even with surroundings.
- *Omnivariance*: Low at LF and MF, moderate HF along the rim.
- *Linearity*: Weak or inconsistent, with localised alignment where the crust follows a geometric feature.

F_H_BUB; OFFSET BUBBLES

Localised, rounded swellings that protrude slightly from smooth surfaces. Typically appear in small clusters or isolated spots, creating vesicle-like outliers not coherent with the object's geometry. Often observed on otherwise regular regions, and likely caused by misaligned point clouds or depth outliers.

- *Confidence*: High at core, lower near perimeter.
- *EdgeLength*: Slightly longer than surroundings, locally irregular.
- *Omnivariance*: Low at LW, Moderate at MF, with sharp rise at HF around the edges.
- *Linearity*: Low throughout, no dominant orientation.

Fig. 9: Zbrush postprocessed screenshots showing examples of High-frequency flaws: *Texture-Induced Microgeometry F_H_TEX* (left) in the “Spino” asset; *Double Skin F_H_SKI* (mid) in the “Sid” asset; *String Ff Pearls F_H_PEA* (mid) in the “Lions” asset.

6. Conclusions

This work introduces a methodological framework for the semantic annotation of flaws in 3D reconstructions, rooted in expert-guided correction and retroactive flaw recognition. Rather than relying on pre-established taxonomies or automated classification, the method is grounded in procedural traceability and localised mesh inspection, supported by geometric and metrological indicators. Its function is not to offer definitive correction strategies, but to systematise and encode the tacit knowledge routinely applied during expert intervention.

The core contribution lies in the operationalisation of this logic: by annotating retroprojected corrections and interpreting them through scalar indicators such as PCA-derived descriptors, edge length, and photogrammetric confidence, the method provides a reproducible substrate for flaw characterisation and its translation into an explicitly formalised form, hence accessible, interoperable and reusable. Furthermore, it enables the emergence of semantically meaningful segmentations, and consolidates a structured record of operator judgement without imposing rigid analytical thresholds.

As a first implementation, the method is applied to a single-operator dataset. The flaw taxonomy derived from this process—while internally coherent and grounded in recurring morphologies—should be regarded as provisional. It demonstrates the viability of the proposed framework and offers a functional basis for mesh diagnosis, but it does not claim exhaustiveness or universal applicability. The taxonomy serves both as an outcome and as a validation mechanism for the method: it tests whether structured, repeatable patterns can be extracted from the correction process, and whether they can support informed classification of geometric anomalies.

7. Future works

Two main developments are envisioned. The first concerns the extension of the method itself as a knowledge collection infrastructure. Its current use is retrospective: it gathers expert decisions, transforms them into structured annotations, and distils them into a semantic taxonomy. This mode will remain valid as the taxonomy evolves, potentially accommodating new reconstruction algorithms, acquisition tools, or object classes. To strengthen its generalisability, the method should be tested across different operators, datasets, and domains, enabling multi-author validation and comparative flaw profiling.

The second development concerns the use of the taxonomy in a predictive direction. Once a sufficient degree of stability is achieved, the annotated segments and their associated descriptors may support analytical classification of flaws directly on RAWp models. This would shift the role of mesh analysis from interpretive aid to diagnostic tool, with indicators acting as proxies for anomaly detection (Figure 10). In such a scenario, classification could be driven by combinations of thresholds, indicator patterns, or trained segmentation deployed within Deep Learning approaches, ultimately enabling integration into semi-automated validation pipelines.

Although these developments exceed the scope of this article, their feasibility is implicitly tested here. The method is designed to be modular, the descriptors are directly extractable, and the segmentation is already semantically structured. A future implementation may embed these properties in a software tool, supporting transparent, explainable, and reproducible flaw analysis in CH digitisation workflows.

Lastly, the taxonomy itself is conceived as an open-ended structure. While its current form is grounded in Depth Map-based reconstruction workflows, its design explicitly accommodates extension to other acquisition methods, surface generation algorithms, and diagnostic practices. This generalisability is not claimed as demonstrated here, but as a deliberate feature of the framework, one that will require future empirical verification across heterogeneous datasets.

Fig. 10: Once the analytical characterisation of flaws within the taxonomy is established, mesh analysis on RAWp can support expert segmentation and tagging of flaws prior to correction, without altering the RAW → DCHOo workflow.

8. Acknowledgements

Blinded for review

9. Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process.

During the preparation of this manuscript, the author used AI-assisted tools (ChatGPT) solely for the purpose of improving the readability and linguistic clarity of the text, which was originally drafted in another language. The use of such tools was conducted under strict human oversight, and the final version was critically reviewed and approved by the author, who takes full responsibility for its accuracy and integrity.

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